

Causes of Misconceptions of Calculation Courses among FUO Science Education Students

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Abstract

The study examined the causes of misconceptions of calculation courses among science education students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. A descriptive design was adopted for the study. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study comprises of final year students Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The sample comprises of fifty four (54) final year science education students. Simple random sampling techniques were used to select the sample size. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled: Misconception On Calculation Course Among Science Education Students {MOCCSES}. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment correlation at 0.05 level of significant. The findings from the study identified poor foundation on mathematics, fear or anxiety about calculation courses, inadequate practice, ineffective teaching methods, students absenteeism from class, lack of learning resources, rote learning, difficult in abstract thinking and improper use of formulas as causes of students misconception on calculation courses which affects their academic grades. Based on the findings it was recommended that educational institutions should implement remedial and support programs that focus on strengthening students' basic understanding of fundamental mathematical concepts and Create opportunities for collaborative learning, such as study groups and peer tutoring, to discuss and clarify concepts together.

Keywords: Causes, Misconceptions, calculations, Science Education

Introduction

Mathematics is a profound and abstract discipline that seeks to understand and describe the truths of the natural world through logical reasoning and rigorous proofs (Penrose, 2020). It is the study of structures, quantities, and relationships using numbers and symbols (Devlin, 2019). Okigbo and Ejikeme, (2017) in their study attested that the modern world will come to a standstill if Mathematics is neglected. Mathematics comprises of topics from simple (topic that are easy to solve) to complex (topics that are technical/difficult to handle). Ekwueme, et al (2012) stated that Mathematics at the junior class has often been taught as a series of steps to follow in order to get the right answer. This made mathematics the science of patterns.

Misconception is a view or opinion that is incorrect because it is based on faulty thinking or comprehension. Inoyapeh (2014) stated that the suggestive of a faulty line of thinking is referred to as a misconception. Misconceptions can give rise to wrong answers due to one's point of view which can be explained, thereby leads to repeated errors. In other words, misconceptions are incorrect understandings of the mathematics. According to Charles-Ogan, (2014) misconceptions

are systematic errors which produce wrong answers, but the arguments that lead to the answers can be explained. Misconception is an erroneous interpretation or difference of opinion that students make based on the teaching methods used which do not follow up the developmental stages of the concept, thereby having a faulty knowledge of the concept like key concepts of graphical quadratic equations.

Okigbo and Ejikeme (2017) surveyed some difficult Mathematics topics in the Senior Secondary School Mathematics curriculum as perceived by student-teachers from University of Lagos, using 60 Sandwich Degree programme students. They opined that student teachers perceived eight topics; trigonometry, probability, arithmetic, latitude, graphs, bearing and distances, construction, and inequalities as difficult to teach. So, if student- teachers find it difficult to teach these difficult concepts like graphs, the students tend to lack foundational understanding which leads to misconception on calculation courses in higher level of education. These misunderstandings may persist, affecting future learning and applications in related fields. Addressing misconceptions promptly is crucial to prevent the accumulation of gaps in knowledge and to foster a solid mathematical understanding.

Misconception in calculation courses among science education students involves

1. Unclear explanations,
2. Lack of foundational understanding,
3. Inadequate practice
4. Tendency to memorize procedures without grasping the underlying concepts
5. Fear or anxiety about the course
6. Ineffective teaching methods
7. Rote learning

Research has shown that many difficulties in learning math stem from students' failure to understand the underlying concepts, which form the basis for the procedures they are using. Identifying and addressing these misconceptions is essential for promoting access and attainment for all students (Schnepper & McCoy, 2017). The understanding of how misconceptions are related to one another and their causes can be useful for identifying broader patterns that affect students' long-term mathematical development (Rakes & Ronau, (2019).

Cognitive psychology plays a pivotal role in understanding how students process and internalize mathematical concepts. Students may develop misconceptions when the cognitive demands of a task exceed their cognitive capacity. Johnson (2008) in his research work focused on comprehensive analysis of the cognitive processes involved in mathematical learning, shedding light on how students develop misconceptions during the acquisition of calculation skills. Her research laid the groundwork for subsequent investigations into the psychological aspects of learning mathematics.

Carter (2011) research work focused on pedagogical approaches in teaching mathematical concepts to science education students. His work identified common teaching methodologies that may inadvertently contribute to student misconceptions, offering valuable insights into the role of instructional methods in shaping students' understanding of mathematical principles.

Technology is an integral part of education; however, the impact of technological tools on mathematical learning is of great value as it has improved the learning. The over reliance on calculators or software without a solid conceptual foundation can lead to surface-level understanding and misconceptions. Martinez (2015) studies delved into the impact of technological tools on mathematical learning. Her findings underscored the need to reconsider the

integration of technology in the classroom, as certain approaches may exacerbate rather than alleviate misconceptions.

Attitudes and interest toward mathematics as a discipline can play an important role among students who study mathematics. Attitude is the sum total of a person's preference for certain types of objects. Broadly, attitude covers all aspects of personality development such as individual interests, motives, values, vocational judgments stemming from vocational pursuits and other phases of one's daily life. An attitude mainly consists of three characteristics: feelings, cognition, and behavior. Attitude is a "like or dislike" feeling. Thompson (2019) in his work focused on the influence of societal perceptions of mathematics on students' attitudes and beliefs. His work revealed the existence of cultural factors that contribute to the development of misconceptions, emphasizing the importance of addressing broader societal influences to enhance mathematics education.

Meanwhile, research on mathematical misconceptions based on gender has significant relevance and interest in the field of mathematics education because it can identify typical error patterns. Research by Else-Quest et al (2010) helped identify patterns of math errors that are common among male and female students. Knowing these differences allows teachers to design more targeted teaching strategies, helping students overcome their mistakes effectively. Understanding the differences in errors between male and female students helps identify aspects of mathematics that may contribute to a lack of self-confidence in female students. By overcoming these mistakes, female students can build their confidence in understanding and mastering mathematics (Gunderson, et al 2012). Research by Eccles (1994) provides teachers and educators with insight into the differences in male and female students' mathematical understanding. With this knowledge, teachers can dig deeper into helping students overcome their mistakes, creating an inclusive and supportive classroom atmosphere.

Statement of the Problem

Limited insight into the root causes of the comprehension of body of knowledge is attributed to common misconceptions in mathematics within the realm of science education. Understanding the cognitive, pedagogical, and contextual factors contributing to these fallacies is crucial for developing targeted interventions that address the core issues of misconceptions of calculation courses that enhances good educational practices. Misconception of the body of knowledge does not only affect students' achievement on mathematical courses but impedes future learning which results into the production of half-baked graduates (Inoyapeh, 2014). The effect of misconception of calculation course which are mainly on science courses is not only on individual but on the society at large; this is because mathematics is the bedrock of science and technology. It is obvious that development of any nation depends on their technological know-how; but the deadly impact of misconception determines the quality of a nation's scientist. Therefore, this study tends to find out the major causes of students' misconception of calculation courses.

Purpose of the Study

This study identifies causes of misconception on calculation courses among Science Education students. The study specifically;

1. Identify causes of FUO science education students' misconception of calculation courses.
2. Examine the impact of identified causes of students' misconception on their academic grade on calculation courses.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised in order to guide the study:

- i. What are the causes of science education students' misconception on calculation courses?
- ii. Do the identified causes of students' misconception affect their academic grade on calculation courses?

Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between identified causes and science education students' misconception of calculation courses.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between identified causes of students' misconception and students' academic grade on calculation courses.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive design which aims to systematically obtain information to describe a phenomenon, using a range of both qualitative research and quantitative data to gather information to make accurate predictions about a particular problem or hypothesis. The population of the study constituted a total of one hundred and twenty five male and female final year students of science education department of FUO in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa state. The sample technique involves a stratified sampling technique that provide low risk and controllable data, the proportional stratified sampling procedures was adopted in selecting 35% of the respondents in each of the department population for the study to arrive at a sample size of 54 students.

The instrument for data collection for this study is structured Likert style questionnaire titled: Misconception On Calculation Course Among Science Education Students {MOCCSES}. The instrument for this research was validated by experts in science education and measurement and evaluation to ensure the inclusion of relevant item and alignment with the study's objective. Cronbach's Alpha formula was used in ascertaining the reliability of the instrument. Reliability coefficient of 0.71 was obtained. The questionnaire were shared among the selected students and retrieved for compilations and analysis. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistic. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation at 0.05 significant level.

Results

Research Question one: What are the causes of science education students' misconception on calculation courses?

Table 2. Mean of responses on Causes of Students Misconception on Calculation Courses and Academic Grade

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of students understanding of basic concept on calculation courses affects their academic grade level.	17	30	5	2	3.15	2.70	Accept
2	Lecturers teaching methods/approaches on calculation courses affect student academic grade level.	27	21	4	2	3.35	2.91	Accept
3	Students' poor/insufficient practice on calculation course affects their academic grade level.	12	26	11	5	2.83	2.44	Accept
4	Students absent during classes on calculation courses affect their academic grade level.	29	21	3	1	3.44	2.99	Accept
5	Lack of students access to learning resources like laboratory, text books, online tutorials affect their academic grade level.	17	23	9	5	2.96	2.58	Accept

Decision: Cutoff mean (X) is 2.00; accept if mean (X) is ≥ 2.00 and reject if mean (x) < 2.00 .

Table 2 result showed that the identified causes of FUO final year science education students misconception on calculation courses affects their academic grade level; following the above result the mean scores of item 1-5 were above the cutoff mean of 2.00, therefore, all the items were accepted. This means that the identified causes of students' misconception affect students' academic grade level. The standard deviations of items 1- 5 are within the range 2.00-3.00 which showed wide range of responses.

Hypothesis one H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between identified causes and science education students misconception of calculation courses.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Analysis Summary of identified causes and misconception.

		Causes	Misconception
Causes	Pearson Correlation	1	.851**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	54	54
Misconception	Pearson Correlation	.851**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	54	54

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation result above showed at sig (2- tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$, proved that there is a significant relationship between identified causes of students misconception and science education students' misconception of calculation courses. The result showed r value of 0.851 which is < 1 indicating a positive strong relationship of 85.1% with p value of .000 at 0.05 significant level.

Hypothesis Two H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between identified causes of students' misconception and student academic grade on calculation courses.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Analysis Summary of identified causes and academic grade. Correlations

		Causes	Grade
Causes	Pearson Correlation	1	.692
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	54	54
Grade	Pearson Correlation	.692	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	54	54

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the correlation result above obtained sig (2- tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$, showed that there is a significant relationship between identified causes of students' misconception and students' academic grade level. The result showed r value of 0.692 which is < 1 indicating a positive strong relationship of 69.2% with p value of .000 at 0.05 significant level.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings of the study in table 1 identified the causes of students' misconception on calculation courses. Table 2, the correlation analysis result showed that there is a significant relationship between identified causes and students' misconception on calculation courses. The findings explained the situation in our higher institutions as regards to students and their struggles on calculation courses especially as it affects their academic grade level. The first finding is supported by the study of Sujarwa and Kurniawan (2019) on analysis of mathematics learning misconception; the study identified students' lack of basic foundation on mathematics concepts as the cause of students' misconception in calculation courses. This is also in agreement with the work of Abidi et al (2021) in their study of students' misconception on algebra which identified poor teaching method as the major cause of students' misconception in algebra. The finding is also supported with the work of Naseer (2015) on analysis of students' errors and misconceptions in pre-university mathematics courses, identified teachers' mode of presentation of mathematical concepts to be the cause of students' errors and misconception in mathematical courses. The study of Turmuzi et al (2024) on misconception of mathematics in higher education identified students' poor foundation on the concept and lack of mastery of the concept as the causes of students' misconception in mathematical course.

The analysis result of table 2 and 4 showed that the identified causes of students' misconception on calculation courses affects their academic grade level. The result also indicated that there is significant relationship between identified causes of students' misconception on calculation courses and students' academic grade level. This study is supported by the work of Verschaffel. et

al (2007) on students' misconception on mathematics and grade achievement, which showed that students' misconception on mathematics (word problem and mathematics modeling) were associated with lower math achievement. The finding is in agreement with the study of Ashcraft (2002) on Math anxiety, cognitive problems; which he identified Math anxiety as the cause to students' misconception and low grade in mathematics courses. Therefore, it came to conclusion that students' misconception on calculation courses affects their academic grade level.

Conclusion

The findings from the study indicated that the identified factors are the causes of students' misconception of calculation courses, reflecting a broader issue in higher education. The results align with previous research, which consistently points to a lack of foundational understanding and poor teaching methods as primary contributors to these misconceptions. These insights underscore the need for educational interventions that strengthen students' foundational knowledge and improve instructional approaches to enhance their performance in calculation courses.

Recommendations

Considering the above findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Educational institutions should implement remedial and support programs that focus on strengthening students' basic understanding of fundamental mathematical concepts to prevent misconception in advanced calculation courses.
2. Create opportunities for collaborative learning, such as study groups and peer tutoring, to discuss and clarify concepts together.

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